

Technological Awareness and Woman Empowerment: An Analytical Study

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Abstract—Technology has shaped people’s lifestyle globally. It facilitates the way to explore new things and enlarge their functioning, organise and effectively manage their potential and facilitates economic opportunities. Women in both developed and developing countries can access learning through technology. The purpose of this research paper is to analyse how technology is driving women empowerment, as technology has changed the way of living, thinking, and behaviour of individuals. As per the united nations SDG 5, there should be enhanced use of information and communication technology, to promote the empowerment of women”. Women constitute around 48% of the population in India and play an active role in social development. New technologies offer huge potential to increase economic opportunities and enhance the women empowerment

Keywords: Women empowerment, Information and Communication technology, Economic opportunities, SDG 5

I. INTRODUCTION

Through technology, women entrepreneurs in the field of e-commerce now have a global platform, overcoming some aspects of conventional mobility culture. Women are receiving more support from their families as well as society to acquire and engage with customers on a worldwide scale when they are at home with their families, taking care of their everyday obligations to them, and enjoying themselves. Women who are active in local e-commerce have elevated the local market, raised awareness, and educated the public. Women empowerment is a basic human and constitutional right of every woman, irrespective of caste, creed, and religion, and a vital part of national development. Women empowerment refers to the process of building a society where women can live peacefully, without any fear of abuse, cruelty, and discrimination, which is very prevalent in a traditional patriarchal society. Women constitute around 48% of the population in India and play an active role in social development, but they are still being suffered and demoralized due to lower social status and fewer rights. Hence, there is a strong need for empowerment and education for women to deal with widespread mistreatment and biases in a male-dominated society. In the term “Empowerment”, power refers to the control over intellectual assets like information, knowledge, and ideas, and material assets like finance and land. Empowerment refers to the multifaceted social development process that helps people to have freedom in all aspects of life. The concept of empowerment consists of social development, economic independence, and political decision-making. Women’s empowerment starts with the understanding of the effects of political and socio-economic forces and awareness of their capabilities and rights. Women are the first exploited creed in mankind’s history and largest overlooked group in the world. Women empowerment is the latest buzzword in India. It enlightens them about what they can do in all segments of life. The most common barrier in women empowerment is that a huge section of women are sidelined and overlooked in the mainstream society. India is a developing country and world’s largest democracy but women here are still affected by deep ignorance about their values in the society. They are discriminated against and deprived in all aspects. Now, gender discrimination exists in India and the world. Women are worshiped as the holy and divine force and they have high position in Upanishads and Vedas. But the reality in progressive society is different. India’s constitution talks about welfare and equality for women, but cruel and barbaric practices still haunt them as female infanticide, fofeticide, dowry issues, child labour, sexual harassment, molestation, rave, gender discrimination, eve-teasing, and domestic violence.

Spiritual leader Swami Vivekananda quoted that, “There is no chance for the welfare of the world unless the condition of women is improved, and it is not possible for a bird to fly on only one wing.” Thus, in order to achieve the status of a developed country, India needs to transform its colossal women force into an effective human resource and this is possible only through the role enhancement of women in financial structure of our social system. We need to shatter some myths like if more women come to marketing field; they will fail sides, their domestic as well as professional. This is grossly under estimated notion as if a woman can manage her home very well; she is naturally having good management skills and can certainly manage an organization as well. Women empowerment means freedom of women from the vicious grips of social, economic, political, caste and gender-based discrimination. It means granting women the power and freedom to make life choices, replacing patriarchy with parity. Empowering women to participate fully in economic life across all sectors is essential to building stronger economies; achieve internationally agreed goals for development and sustainability. In this regard, there are various types of women empowerments, such as follows:

- **Individual Empowerment** – A female is a being with her senses, imagination, and thoughts; she should be given a proper environment to express her thoughts freely.

- **Social Empowerment**—society belongs to women same as to any privileged men. There should be no place for concepts like ‘gender’ and the ones come on state to promote gender equality. Gender equality is something in which female and male enjoy the same opportunities, outcomes, rights and obligations in all spheres of life.
- **Educational Empowerment**—empowering girls with the knowledge, skills, and self-confidence is the need of hour. This will help women to get aware of their rights and will cultivate a healthy morale to claim them.
- **Economic Empowerment**—In India it literally means to get rid of financial dependence from their male counterparts. This economic subjugation leads to social subjugation.
- **Legal Empowerment**—it speaks of a comprehensive legal structure which is sensitive of women rights. It should be based on rule of law, not the rule of land.
- **Political Empowerment**—a participative political system should be there, which is inclusive in all means of social representations. Women can lead only when the decision-making opportunities are given to them in government and legislative branch.

Unfortunately, women in India have always been seen as a gender which is best suitable for domestic work and not as a mainstream economic contributor. The deep-seated patriarchal ideology is still continuing and is visible in the start-up ecosystem where the number of woman entrepreneurs is hideously low. To balance this Economic development of women is needed, only this is the most effective way to empower and emancipate women, and this in turn will further the economic development of the country by their active participation in labour force. Only the economic empowerment of women can have far reaching effects. It can change the gender equations both inside and outside the house, helping them to overcome the fear of helplessness and powerlessness. Therefore, it is the high time we need to remove this gender asymmetry from our economic system.

This study examined women's empowerment and technical awareness but through India's technical education system with a particular focus on the MDG-3 goal. 48.26% of India's 1, 028, 6 million people are women, according to census 2001. They range in age from 15 to 29 by about 27%. Between 1951 and 2001, women's literacy rates increased from 7.83% to 54.16%. Nonetheless, 228 million women are still regarded as illiterate. Out of all the people who enrolled in Class 1, just 6% of women who completed their secondary school went on to pursue further education. Thus, it is evident that many women in India are still not enrolled in the country's current higher education system. According to data, women make up only 33% of the labour force in India but almost 50% of the adult population. They put in about 66% of all working hours, earn 10% of the global average, and possess less than 1% of all real estate. Relatively few women have the ability to impact political beliefs or the process of making decisions (Pillai, 1995).

The empowering role of women's education affects not only the lives of the women, but also the lives of their children and other dependents – such as the aged. Education especially professional and technical education - is also likely to enhance women's economic independence by equipping them with the skills necessary to take up paid employment opportunities. At the national level, educating women has resulted in improved productivity, improved income and economic development, as well as in a better quality of life, leading to a notably healthier and better nourished population. As stated by *Nancy Pelosi*, “Women are leaders everywhere you look – from the CEO who runs a Fortune 500 company to the housewife who raises her children and heads her household. Our country was built by strong women, and we will continue to break down walls and defy stereotypes.”

I.I. LITERATURE REVIEW

Linda Mayoux (2001) described the role of women is increasingly recognized in the development of the Third World Nations particularly in collective groups or cooperatives in rural areas. Lenz (2010) has also stated that women constitute about half of the world population and contribute about two-third of all the labour hours worked by the human race, though they are the primary providers of childcare and suppliers of many of the necessities of day-to-day life for themselves and their families. Women play a major role in the formal economies regulated by society and continue to be a large part of the informal economies. According to prediction by National Association of Software and Services Companies (NASSCOM), by 2014 there will be one and a half million jobs in the IT enabled services. If 50% to 70% of these jobs were to go to women, the impact will be tremendous. Ms. Ruchi Malhotra (2015) concluded that the women is empowered through the help of technology used in marketing field. It has changed their position from past to present. The development of IT has enabled the women section to participate in each and every walk of life. It has empowered the women by enhancing their skills, knowledge and income.

Vishal Monga (2018) concluded in his study that as the industry is cognizant of women's role in ICT industry, there is a sea change to attract women employees. Balancing act of family and job-related issues are making a dent in MMG and SMG level women in various companies. This can be a blessing in disguise as they can use their skill, knowledge, and experience to become a successful Entrepreneur. Top level women employees are setting examples for younger generation. They have to walk a tightrope and make a fine balancing act to excel in their carrier in IT related fields. Bindu Tiwari and Dr Naveen Kumar

(2018) analyzed that better understanding capacity of women makes them on demand for marketing jobs, but to note how marketing supports in women education, employment and empowerment. Online marketing tools have made them easy learning, which is supporting women education, better employment with good pay scale supports in women employment and financial and intellectual independence makes women empowered. Parwinder Kaur & Rashmi Gujrati (2021) said about to demonstrate the strategies promoting the use of new technologies in developing countries should take into account the benefits of increasing female participation in the labour market. To popularize the digital technologies and services required to develop firms and female entrepreneurship, the government should strengthen digital inclusion associated with financial inclusion. Harvinder Singh & Deepak Kumar stated that to empower the women, information and communication technology plays an important role, but it good initiatives that Government can take to raise funds for running these programmes. There are various tools like smart phone, computers, but these too depend on ICT. Government programme of distributing tablets to school going children's is an important initiative towards digital empowerment. Tabasum Niroo, W., & Crompton, H.

(2022) This study is among the first systematic reviews exploring how technology enhances access to learning materials for women's empowerment globally. The study identified five key industries impacted: health, agriculture, environment, entrepreneurship, and communication. Notably, agriculture trends revealed a bias towards men in roles and women in households. Mobile devices were a prevalent technology, offering functionality, internet access, and portability. The findings highlighted three empowering themes for women: health, communications, and entrepreneurship, providing agency and resources for decision-making. Azmul Haque, Wazedul Haque, Ehashan Ahmed & Zaedul Islam (2023) This study highlighted the substantial potential of the IT sector in promoting gender equality in Bangladesh, stressing the need for collaborative efforts from diverse stakeholders. Future research could focus on empirical studies to quantify the sector's impact on women's lives, laying the groundwork for more targeted interventions. Overall, this study serves as an initial step towards harnessing the IT sector for sustainable women's empowerment in Bangladesh, aiming to contribute to academic discussions and drive real-world change. Dr. Raziabegum.A. Nadaf (2024) As per the study, a significant number of women enroll in ICT training with the goal of enhancing their quality of life. This involves acquiring new skills, improving their work capabilities, and expanding job opportunities, all with the aim of achieving financial independence. The analysis indicated that, irrespective of employment status, most women experienced an improvement in their ability to achieve financial autonomy. The study emphasizes the broader benefits of economic growth and prosperity through the involvement of women in science and technology. The study advocates for recognizing and incorporating women's participation in science and technology as an essential component of overall economic development strategies. It highlights the government's crucial role in providing the necessary social infrastructure and a conducive political environment for women to enter the fields of science and technology.

I.II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the technological growth and women empowerment.
- To study the role of technology in women empowerment.
- To give suggestions for using technology and enhance women empowerment.

I.III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of supporting the material in this study and presenting the state of women's education in India today, secondary data has been gathered. For this study, secondary data and information were gathered from a variety of sources, including government publications, books, periodicals, journals, research articles, and reliable websites.

II. TECHNOLOGICAL GROWTH AND WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Rural women can benefit from increased access to and comprehension of technology by becoming more knowledgeable about many facets of life-turns. An ordinary woman into a businessman by giving her the know-how and inspiration to use her talents such as cooking, weaving, stitching, pottery, etc. to start and manage. Pprofitable businesses helps small enterprises by removing intermediaries and the necessity for a physical market, providing simple access to resources, and offering guidance through expertise and information. Working from home is still possible for women who, due to personal circumstances or unintentional job termination after giving birth, can do it online. The ease with which raw materials and final product/service clients can now be accessed through the online market has made it easier for women to do business. The proliferation of online courses provides a means for women whose mobility is restricted to pursue higher education. Numerous smartphone apps provide women with timely health or other information needs. On social media, women can learn about and express their opinions on a range of topics.

Because gender equality entails equal rights, opportunities, and access to resources for men and women alike, digitization has enabled people to advance their careers. They now have the opportunity to work from home, take care of their family, and yet succeed in their careers. Technology has been a major factor in putting women on par with males in the modern era. Women are becoming more aware of digital platforms to educate and upskill themselves as a result of technological improvements and easier access to it. They can now participate in online knowledge-sharing sessions and communicate with anyone in the world via digital platforms. To empower the women, information and communication technology plays an important role, but it good initiatives that Government can take to raise funds for running these programmes. There are various tools like smart phone, computers, but these too depend on ICT. Government programme of distributing tablets to school going children’s is an important initiative towards digital empowerment.

III. ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

The advancement of technology has opened up new opportunities for women to gain economic power and can support greater gender parity in the workplace. But because of gender biases in technology, there aren't enough women in technical fields, and companies need to do more to close the gender gap. To create a more diverse and technologically sound world, organizations need to take advantage of this chance to give women access to knowledge and information. We have implemented an initiative whereby we allow our female employees—who comprise approximately 90% of our workforce—to work from home.

With the help of technology, women are finding it simpler to start businesses, obtain employment, and pursue education while shattering preconceived notions about gender. Technological developments have the potential to remove obstacles that stand in the way of women's success and allow them to fully engage in the economy, from possibilities to pursue economic and financial independence to access to healthcare and education. Women now have more opportunities for economic empowerment thanks to the digital transformation, which has also increased gender equality. With the help of technology, women now have more chances to enter and thrive in the workforce, dismantling obstacles and promoting greater gender equality. Through technology, a more varied and inclusive future where everyone may succeed regardless of gender is becoming possible. Examples of this include remote work, flexible scheduling, online education, and mentor ship programs. Research centered on how technology helped women and girls become more informed about their bodies, breastfeeding, diets, and general health literacy. In present time to know the importance of technology in women empowerment Govt. has themed the International Women's Day, 8 March 2023 (IWD 2023) as "Digital: Innovation and Technology for Gender Equality"

Technology is helpful to enhancing the women empowerment in all aspect of life -

- Women can be empowered by learning different digital skills.
- Women can increase accessibility through technology.
- Women can showcase their potential skills through online presentation
- Women can expand their expertise and explore new opportunities through online participation in seminars, workshops, conferences, forums.
- Through technology women can stay organised, updated and can manage their time effectively.
- Women can empower themselves by advocating for gender equality, and make their workplace safe and more inclusive.
- Post maternity they can engage themselves with their work from home. This will bring financial as well as social security.
- Explore new areas apart from intellectual services like stitching, pottery, cooking, gardening etc.

Eric Berridge, CEO of Bluewolf, an IBM Company, stated “Workplaces that support gender diversity also tend to have more flexible work-life balance and family leave policies, things that both sexes value and that increase women’s ability to participate equally in the workforce.”

IV. SUGGESTIONS FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH TECHNOLOGY

Globally, technology has influenced people's lifestyles. With the vast array of educational resources at their disposal, technology is becoming the primary means of assistance for most people on the planet. Technology gives women access to education in both rich and developing nations, but the academic community lacks a current understanding of how technology is being used to deliver learning resources that will empower women worldwide.

41.25% female population are illiterate out of 662.90 million female population of India and do not meet the basic educational requirements. This leaves them in low-paying jobs where they are always in need of money. Most rural women spend more time taking care of their families, working on farms, raising cattle, raising poultry, and other related activities to generate income and meet their basic needs.

IV.I. STRATEGIES TO EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN IN TECHNOLOGY

- **Opportunity to speak all women**

It should be common knowledge for managers to be aware of the many working styles that employees can adopt. When speaking at a table, women's voices might often be muffled, so if they don't feel overqualified, they may be less afraid to speak up on certain topics. It is crucial for managers and leaders in an organization to support women in speaking up and stepping outside of their comfort zones. During meetings, make sure to include everyone and don't let the loudest voices get the most attention.

- **Establish a network of women**

The number of women who appreciate having a women's network in their workplace or in general is startling. The gender composition of a woman's network has a significant influence on her career; therefore creating these groups can empower women in technology. If your company doesn't already have a women's organization, you can start one online or recommend one to your boss. This will not only benefit the current women in the company but also assist draw in new members for future recruiting.

Sponsoring women in a women's network is particularly advantageous because studies indicate that their paths to success as female tech professionals will be more significant. In the sense of picking up new skills, being sponsored by a woman is

comparable to finding a mentor for her; yet, it differs in that the person sponsoring you has the ability to recommend you for important positions inside the organization.

- **Provide assistance**

Giving women in technology chances within an organization can be a great way to encourage and empower them. Implementing mentoring programs, coding workshops, and leadership training in your organization are a few examples of these options to boost women's development. In addition to supporting women who are currently employed by an organization, using these various programs can aid in luring in new female candidates. By demonstrating this support, a varied pool of highly qualified female candidates for tech jobs, as well as role models and leaders, will emerge to assist new female hires. Recognizing women in technology for their accomplishments by sharing the news with the entire organization or submitting them for awards is another method to empower and support them. This recognition can inspire more women to believe in themselves and perform to the best of their ability by providing them with the visibility that not all women in technology receive.

- **Acknowledge prejudice based on gender**

When attempting to empower women in technology, it is important to recognize that there might not be an even playing field. It is generally simple to ignore, and occasionally it is overlooked unconsciously. To empower women in technology, an organization's entire workforce must be cognizant of gender bias. For instance, you should review your regulations to make sure gender bias isn't occurring if you are more forgiving of a guy arriving late due to traffic than a woman who needs to take care of childcare. Organizations can become more inclusive by acknowledging gender prejudices and incorporating them into their culture. Creating a diverse culture and empowering women in technology can be achieved through modelling inclusive behaviour. To make sure that women's opinions are heard and that they feel involved in choices that impact them, those in positions of leadership should initiate talks with other staff members and women.

IV.II. DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY'S BENEFITS FOR WORKING WOMEN

- By providing platforms for women to openly express and share their experiences, worries, and expertise, information technology has accelerated the process of women's empowerment and created opportunities for their continued enrichment.
- The utilisation of information technology has expanded the range of their operations and made it possible for them to handle problems that were previously outside of their purview. It gave women a clear window to the outside world.
- They receive information without any censorship or distortion. This results in a broader perspective and a deeper comprehension of their current circumstances.
- Technology has also significantly altered how people think about their jobs and work spaces. Women now enjoy flexible work schedules and the ability to work from home.
- Time and distance no longer have as much of an impact on how business and production-related tasks are organized because to IT. Due to technology, women are now performing a large share of the occupations that large companies outsource.
- IT gives women time and space flexibility. As a result, women may work whenever they want, from anywhere, usually from the comfort of their own homes, and generate additional revenue to help them become more financially independent and powerful.
- For women, new career fields like telemarketing and medical transcriptions, among others, have created a wealth of work options. Even though these positions are undoubtedly underpaid and in the bottom echelon of IT jobs, they are creating opportunities where none previously existed.

Through technology, women entrepreneurs in the e-commerce sector now have a global platform, circumventing some of the traditional mobility culture. Women are receiving more support from their families and society as a whole to acquire and engage with customers on a worldwide scale when they are at home with their families, taking care of their everyday obligations to them, and enjoying themselves. Women who are active in local e-commerce have elevated the local market, raising awareness and educating the public. Because of the pandemic, working virtually or remotely appears to be commonplace. Because digital technology allows for greater workplace flexibility, it has made working for female employees safer. Given that most businesses allow employees to work from home, more and more women are eager to start working. When more women are leaving the house for work and utilizing technology to do so conveniently from their secure and flexible home, it has the potential to close the gender equality gap.

While raising children is a reason why many women choose to give up their employment, there are numerous instances in which they are left with no other option. Few companies even consider key aspects of parenthood like breastfeeding; much less provide the room or comfort to do so. Women are finding it easier to juggle the obligations of parenthood and work from the comfort of their homes as digital communication increasingly replaces traditional forms of contact, even in the business sector. Consider how much brain equity we are recovering collectively as a world.

The population of India in 2020, as reported by the World Bank, is composed of 65.05 percent rural residents. There are 662.90 million women living in India. The percentage of females in the population is 48.04 percent, while the percentage of males is 51.96 percent. According to the 2011 census, 41.25% of women do not have even the most basic education. Women who lack education are inevitably forced into low-paying jobs where they must make ends meet. The majority of rural women who stay work longer hours in farms, doing home duties, or engaging in related agricultural activities like raising cattle, farming poultry, dairying, etc. They are deprived of an education in order to generate income and meet their fundamental requirements.

We have been taught for many years that women are in constant competition with one another. For scarce jobs, for the superior figure, the flawless face, the perfect man. However, this is just untrue. We've been given this narrative for far too long. Women desire that from the Internet. Sadly, it's not always possible for them to form genuine friendships on the uncensored, unpoliced open Internet.

"If you are digitally fluent, it can provide a positive effect throughout your entire career lifecycle, and the effect benefits women more than men," according to an Accenture report titled "Getting To Equal: How Digital is Helping Close the Gender Gap at Work." It goes on to say that, "if governments and businesses can double the pace at which women become frequent users of technology, we could reach gender equality in the workplace by 2040 in developed nations and by 2060 in developing nations." Regretfully, when it comes to women's digital fluency, India continues to receive the lowest overall score of any nation. If we want to move forward as a group, we need all examine this carefully and thoroughly. With a large portion of the population living in rural areas, India is a developing nation where crimes against women, including domestic violence, remain a serious problem. Women in rural areas face discrimination based on both social status and caste. The patriarchal system prevalent in rural India is another barrier to women's technological empowerment. Women's empowerment is hampered by the lack of access to financial stability, healthcare, and education that results from all of these societal barriers.

V. CONCLUSION

Women cannot be empowered through entrepreneurship if the necessary starting money is not available. Women now have the chance to launch their own businesses with little startup costs and readily available resources thanks to digitalization and e-commerce. The number of start-ups in the market has increased as a result of new social media platforms that offer ideal venues for exhibiting the tasks in order of gifted women while they are at home and making money from it. Various Indian states Government initiatives and associations aim to empower women through participation in different sectors. Examples include SEWA in Gujarat, Gyandoot in Madhya Pradesh, M.S. Swaminathan Research Project in Pondicherry, Smile in Pune, Datamation Foundation in Delhi, and Aamagaon Soochna Kendra in Orissa. These efforts focus on leveraging Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to enhance women's involvement in economic activities.

E-commerce has emerged as a significant avenue for women entrepreneurs, providing them with financial freedom and the ability to tap into the global market with minimal initial investment. The key challenge is to raise awareness among women about e-commerce and provide them with the necessary training to use social media platforms for business effectively. This approach not only contributes to economic empowerment but also enhances social status and financial independence for women.

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